

CULTIVATION OF CARTOON MOVIES EFFECTS ON SCHOOL GOING CHILDREN OF SARGODHA

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Abstract

Cartoons are an important form of communication in the media and have big effects on viewers, especially children. This study examines how cartoon movies affect school-age children of Sargodha. Convenience sampling is used to pick 240 respondents for data gathering. Government schools both inside and outside of Sargodha city provided the sample. For data analysis, interpretation, and inference, statistical methods like correlation and chi-square are employed. Research indicates that children watch cartoon movies very much, and that girls watch cartoons more than boys. Children in the Sargodha region enjoy and comprehend Hindi language, although they slightly favor using its phrases or sentences in everyday conversation. Male children in the lower age group (5-8 years) and lower education group (primary school) are more likely to involve in fighting after watching cartoon movies. Male children receive higher grades (A) than female children. The majority of children receive B grades in their previous class, and viewing television, particularly cartoons, has significant effects on their academic performance. The children's parents also stated that viewing cartoon movies poses a greater risk to their children's health in terms of ocular weakness than obesity and sleep disorders. Parents believe that watching cartoon movies has a greater effect on their children's attention span than on their conduct, academic achievement, health, or language. Overall results indicate that cartoons have greater influence on children who watch more cartoon movies.

INTRODUCTION

Unpleasant emotional responses to violence and the observant acquisition of ideas and scripts are the two main causes of the consequences of cartoon films. Because complexity and observational learning both depend on the observer's readily influenced mind. Adults may react at the moment, things eventually return to normal as children retain what they see and may recall when needed (Gökçeşlan, 2010). As a result, children are exposed to cartoons that depict violence and actions for long period. Priming and imitation of particular acts may potentially have short-term effects, long-term consequences are mostly brought about by long-term observational learning of cognitions that underlie violence. Psychologists have demonstrated that children's minds quickly pick up on and mimic everything they exposed. Young brains can be shaped into anything they are exposed to, much like a wet clay.

Cartoons have also a positive effect on children and may be categorized in a variety of ways to help them better comprehend and explore their life (Gandhar et al., 2016). According to neurologists and cognitive psychologists, the human mind functions as an associative network where concepts are partially triggered, or primed, by catalysts with which they are related. Children's mental development is positively effect by cartoon movies. Numerous research has discovered that children who watch cartoons are more adept at applying logic than children who don't watch cartoons. It broadens their perspective on society as a whole and makes them aware of their personal responsibility and part in it. One may argue that cartoon movies are incredibly beneficial to children' brain growth (Ghilzai et al., 2017).

The cognitive learning method states that learning is comprehension via the experience of cognitive functions as thinking, recalling, and seeing. Children's cognitive development includes the gradual improvement of learning abilities including focus, memory, and information processing. These essential abilities help children process the information they encounter and eventually learn how to assess, analyze, recall, compare, and comprehend cause and consequence. The majority of cognitive skills are learnt, even though some are influenced by a child's genetic composition (Han et al., 2007). Cartoons have a significant effect on children's

vocabulary since they spend more time viewing them than studying. Children in Pakistan benefit from seeing Hindi and English-language content because it helps them become more fluent in a second language and teaches them when to utilize certain words. Additionally, this raises their academic language scores. Compared to other children and teens, children who watch cartoon movies in foreign languages typically possess stronger command. Children who watch instructional cartoons do better academically, gain high marks, and are more creative than those who watch violent cartoons. It is said that cartoons assist children speak English fluently. Cartoonish education, which is very effective instrument for enhancing skills and critical thinking, is one way to improve the abilities and performance of school-age children. Audio-visual communications are easier for children to process than reading (Yorulmaz, 2022).

Cartoons engage children, and their use of comedy helps children learn without becoming disinterested in class and captures their attention. Children's education can benefit from television. Children engage in some sort of learning process as they watch cartoons (Kirkorian et al., 2008). Children are exposed to mass media while learning from their environment, which includes their parents. Since it is the media genre that children watch the most, some of it is accentuated by the media, while others come from many sources on the nature of learning that is crucial. Researchers discovered slight negative correlations between children's academic performance and the amount of time they spend watching television. Cartoons have had a significant effect on children's behavioral development for the past ten years.

Using cartoon movies for academic purpose, it helps lessen disinterest as well as academic stress, anxiety, and disruptive conduct (Fisch, 2012). Children's cartoon movies and the material they contain are essential to one another. The pleasant animation significantly improves children's social behavior development. They learn and practice much of observable behaviors from watching cartoon movies (Alam et al., 2023). Although, viewing cartoons has certain benefits, there is a clear detrimental correlation between media exposure and academic

performance. Additionally, it has certain detrimental effects on the physical and mental health of children and teenagers. In addition, the effects of various media devices are categorized based on knowledge. Compared to children without TV set in their bedroom, those children watch more than an hour of TV, which leads to poor academic performance as well as social and physical boredom. Television has become the main common source of entertainment-based socialization as it is centralized narrative system that brings comparatively logical universe of similar visuals and messages into every home. Many individuals who were not previously part of the global common culture are now part of this technology era, often known as the machine age (Kondo, & Steemers, 2007).

Significance of the Study

Since children are the nation's future and the leaders of the next generation, media genres have big effects on how they grow in this day and age. They are exposed to variety of content, which affects them both physically and psychologically. Cartoon movies that are imported from other nations and either dubbed in their native tongue through localization processes also have an effects on social norms and values (Gunter & Gunter, 2019). They also have an effects on academic learning, and prolonged viewing of these movies can result in poorer grades and lack of creative thinking. Their naive minds are unaware of the negative effects cartoons have on them. Violent material can cause them bodily pain or even death (Rice et al., 982). Children's physical and mental health can be effected by cartoon movies in both positive and bad ways. Its good consequences include developing a youngster with high cognitive and observable activity, as well as teaching them about life patterns. On the other hand, negative influences cause children to acquire harmful behavior of children.

Objectives of Research Study

- To examine the amount of time spent watching and the exposure level o children.
- To determine the relationship between their exposure to watching habits and their physical well-beings

- To find out what the children are receiving from cartoons and how the cartoons are influencing them.

Research Question of Study

- How much time do children spend watching cartoons, and what is the level of exposure they experience?
- What is the relationship between children's cartoon-watching habits and their physical well-being (e.g., sleep patterns, physical activity, vision, eating habits)?
- How do cartoons influence children's behavior, language, and social interactions?

Literature Review

Animation is one of the methods used to teach children through cartoon movies. Margarita (2023) employed cartoon animation, which is the costliest and challenging to create and pinpoint the foreign influence on local culture across world. The remainder of the world must import animation material since just a small number of nations has the necessary skills. Japan and the United States of America have established two significant traditions, anime and animated cartoons (Napier, 2001). Since it primarily reflects the cultural, traditional, social, and religious values of the place where it is produced and it contains cultural elements also. The dubbing process is used to make it more comprehensible for the local audience, but it retains the original visuals, which include images of things like eating, dressing, living standards, and behavior.

The cartoon movies are imported into nearly every other country in the world. Children who were older and those learning English as a second language were able to draw more complex parallels between Mexican and American cultures. There are many anime and manga enthusiasts, creating an otaku community. Anime and manga have had brief surges in popularity both in Japan and the West. Anime is now regarded as a recognized style of animation and is seen as a representation of Japanese modern culture globally. Research on the effects of cartoon viewing on children, teens, and adults revealed that those who have children under the age of twelve at home like watching animated cartoons. This effects are more pronounced for parents from older generations, who

are less likely to enjoy anime. Regarding popular culture, there should be less discussion of how TV may be utilized to educate children more than just what society believes they should know (Arshad et al., 2018).

Physical Effects of Cartoons Watching

Aslan et al., (2021) highlights the use of cartoons as a psychological teaching method. While they may need less cognitive processing for understanding, cartoons are an excellent source of linguistic input, and watching them might help students feel less bored and less stressed about their studies. Visual messages help children learn more effectively and have been shown to boost cognitive development and academic performance. Compared to the conventional approach, using cartoons to teach grammar and educating students through audio and video improves language proficiency, motivates them for the course, and boosts educational engagement among children (Atabey, 2021).

Effects of Cartoon on Behavior Development

Child's conduct was initially shaped by their family and school. Family has an effects on children's psychological development since it establishes the groundwork for the growth of a positive personality in maturity. The school assumes a role in the development of child's moral, social, cognitive, and phonological skills. One of the most common mediums that has an effects on children's life is television. The youngster is exposed to a wide range of television programs, including cartoon movies, sports, movies, serials, commercials, and more. Children begin watching television cartoon movies at the age of six months in order to recognize the items, and by the time they are two or three years old, they are avid watchers (Ulubeyli et al., 2015).

Effects of Violent Cartoon Contents on Children

Children at school who witness violence are more prone to experience more sleep disturbances. Children who see violence in their families or communities exhibit immature conduct, sleep disturbances, mental anguish and anxiety, loneliness worries, and linguistic regression. The demographics of the children's household determine how much exposure they receive to various forms of violence.

low-income neighborhoods, expertise (Nada, 2016). Children in urban schools rarely see chronic neighborhood violence because they are oblivious to certain harmful practices. It appears that those who reside in lower socioeconomic areas are rarely exposed to communal violence. Even though they frequently featured more violent content than a "real" show, they were still entertaining because, in reality, no one is harmed by television, which fosters dialogue and play among children and improves their skills, knowledge, and understanding of social reality (Cappuccio, 2017).

Theoretical Framework

According to Gerbner et al. (1986), light viewers are people who watch television for two hours or less in a single day. Since children are exposed to media in a variety of forms, watching cartoons is considered to take up less time than the two hours. According to the concept of mainstreaming, viewers of television adopt habits that are influenced by various cultural, societal, and demographic factors. Cultivation theory explains the phenomena wherein a viewer's perception of reality is distorted by visual violence, leading him to perceive the world as more perilous and deadly. This phenomena, which Gerbner (1988) dubbed the Mean World Index, supports mainstreaming. The cultivation effect may be enhanced by occurrences that viewers witness in real life and on television. People's daily lives and television viewing deliver a double dose of messages that resonate to intensify the cultivation. This study is important because cartoon movies have a variety of effects on children, and children who watch more of them may develop regulated behavior and perceptions about them, which is pertinent to this abandonment.

Social Learning Theory

Bandura's studies on the impact of electronic media on kids explains that, social learning occurs well through television. Most of the learning is stored in the memory to later produce such behavior at the time of necessity. According to Bandura (2009), the media has a "multi pattern flow of influence." Children's memory is quite effective; they can retain a much of information and recall it later. They also don't forget behaviors that they have learnt from the media. They are very skilled at imitating and copying, and media messages have the power to sway viewers with their

range of positive messages that promote collaboration, kindness, good manners, and other virtues. The social learning theory was examined in relation to how the variables and constructs included in this study represent its three primary components: cognition, behavior, and environment (Lee, & LaRose, 2007). The fundamental tenet of social learning theory is that children pick up behaviors from watching them on TV.

Research Methodology

For some demographic groups, such children or the illiterate, the survey technique may not be suitable or

feasible since the questions must be written and explained in way that allows respondents to read, comprehend, and meaningfully reply to them. After gathering a sample of respondents at a predetermined location and time, each respondent is questioned and asked to complete the survey questionnaire. The researcher finds it to be an easy format that guarantees a high response rate. They might ask the researcher for clarification if they continue to have trouble comprehending a particular question.

Table 4.1 Geographical Division of Respondents

	No. of Students	No. of Male Students	No. of Female Students	(n=)
Students from Urban areas	120	60	60	120
Students from Rural areas	120	60	60	120
Total respondent	240	120	120	240

No. of responses (n=240)

Sampling Methods

In order to measure the effects, the convenience sampling strategy was employed in this research article to gather data from the target respondents. This technique was chosen since questionnaires were given to respondents who are enrolled in school. Additionally, each question was explained to them in order to improve their capacity for ways to providing proper answers. Since more than half of the students attend private schools, there is no census or record of all enrolled children. As a result, as was previously indicated, the sampling approach does not provide every student an equal chance of being included in the sample. As a result, there was no student sample framework from which a sample could be drawn at random to guarantee that every student had an equal chance of being included in the sample. Convenience sampling is the methodical picking of items in situations where it is extremely challenging to identify every item in a population.

Instrument of Survey Data Collection

In survey research, a range of methods are employed to gather data. This research uses a systematic,

confirmed questionnaire to gather data on how cartoon movies affect school-age children. Questionnaire was created by the researcher with the assistance of the research supervisor. Section A of the questionnaire was created to gather personal and demographic data from the respondents, including sex, age, location, body mass index, and education. Section B of the questionnaire consists of 19 questions that focus on the various aspects of the respondents' behavior and perceptions regarding the particular study subjects.

Large-scale data collecting is a part of research. Data analysis reduces the collected data to make it beautiful, useful, and intelligible. Data reduction is strategy used to ease analysis and storage issues and provide researchers with more context after data collecting. For computer analysis, the collected data was transformed into labels and given codes, letters, and numbers through SPSS. The data analysis chapter uses Microsoft Word, Excel, and SPSS 22.0 to evaluate, analyze, and edit survey research data. Frequencies, percentages, the Pearson correlation formula is used to show and measure the collected data in tables and figures.

Figure 4.1 Children Interest in Contents of Cartoon Programs

Children's interest in watching cartoon series material is demonstrated by the data in Figure 4.1. According to data analysis, children generally prefer to watch "educational cartoons" (48.8%) over comedy cartoons (46.3%), violent and combative cartoons (40.0%), horror cartoons (37.5%), and cartoons based on love and romance stories (29.6%). Children prefer to watch educational cartoons very much (48.8%), much (15.0%), and somewhat (11.7%) above their rarely (7.9%) and not at all (16.7%) categories, according to the unique investigation of interest in

"educational cartoons. In light of this, children who score highly (37.5%), significantly (14.6%), and slightly (23.3%) like "horror cartoons" are more likely to watch them than those who score rarely (11.7%) and not at all (12.9%). In a similar vein, children who are in the very much (40.0%), much (18.8%), and somewhat (18.8%) categories of loving "fighting and aggressive cartoons" are more likely to do so than those who are in the rarely (7.5%) and not at all (15.0%) groups.

Figure 4.2 Frequency of Children Involvement of Behavior After Watching Cartoon

Above figure 4.2 explains the frequency of children involvement of behavior after watching cartoon. Comparably, data research on "involvement in fighting" reveals that children who watch cartoon programs are more likely to become aggressive and engage in fighting very much (27.5%), much (5.0%), and somewhat (14.6%) than those who watch them rarely (14.6%) and not at all (38.3%). According to the data analysis on "increase asking questions," children are more likely to ask their parents questions

after viewing cartoon programs in the very much (21.7%), much (28.3%), and somewhat (17.5%) categories than in the rarely (12.9%) and not at all (19.6%) categories. In a similar vein, the data analysis of "want to Practice what they watch" reveals that children who watch cartoon programs are more likely to want to practice what they watch (27.1%), considerably (22.9%), and somewhat (20.0%) than those who watch them infrequently (9.2%) or not at all (20.8%).

Table 4.2 Statistics: Children Exposure to Horror Cartoons and Production of Frightened Behavior

		Stress Anxiety & Frightened behavior After Watching Cartoons
Watch Horror Cartoon	Pearson Correlation	.166**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.010
	N*	240

*No. of responses (n=240) **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Through the use of a correlation test, the relationship between children's preference for watching horror-themed cartoon movies and their displays of stress, anxiety, and fear was examined. The findings show a

highly significant relationship between these two behaviors.

The results also showed that children's overall participation increased after viewing cartoons.

Table 4.3 Statistics: watching fighting contents and children involvement in fighting (Chi-Square Tests)

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	19.408 ^a	16	.248
Likelihood Ratio	20.719	16	.190
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.069	1	.080
N of Valid Cases*	240		

*No. of responses (n=240)

The Chi-square test was used to examine the relationship between children's preference for watching violent cartoon movies and their involvement in fighting. The findings show that there is a stronger correlation between children's preference for watching violent cartoon movies and their involvement in fighting after watching them. The frequency of children's predilection for viewing cartoon movies with violent content and their engagement in fighting after watching cartoons movies. The main result from the Pearson Chi-Square test gave a value of 19.408^a with 16 degrees of freedom, and the significance level (p-value) was 0.248. Since this p-value is greater than 0.05, it means

the result is not statistically significant. In simple words, there is no strong evidence that the two variables are related any differences in the data could have happened by chance. The Likelihood Ratio test, which is a supporting test, gave a similar result with a p-value of 0.190. This also suggests that there is no meaningful association between the variables. There was also a Linear-by-Linear association result, with a value of 3.069 and p-value of 0.080. This value is closer to being significant but still higher than 0.05, so again, we do not have enough evidence to say there's a clear pattern or trend in the data. Finally, test included 240 valid responses, which is a good sample size.

Figure 4.3 Frequency of Children Liking of Cartoon Components

Above figure 4.3 explains the frequency of children liking of cartoon components. The "children's copy of favorite cartoon characters' components shown in cartoon programs" is depicted in the data analysis, children generally tend to imitate "dressing" more than they do language (38.8%), body movements (34.6%), and eating style (24.2%). Compared to their rarely (4.6%) and not all (28.8%) groups, children very much (42.9%), much (12.1%), and somewhat (11.7%) replicate cartoon character dresses, according to the exclusive analysis. Children like to copy language very much (38.8%), considerably (29.6%), and slightly

(8.8%) more than they do infrequently (4.2%) and not at all (18.8%), according to the copy "Language" examination. Therefore, based on an exclusive investigation, children mimic cartoon characters' "Eating Style" very much (24.2%), much (20.0%), and somewhat (20.4%) more than they do in their rarely (7.1%) and not all (28.3%) categories. In comparison to their rarely (12.1%) and not all (20.0%) categories, children very much (34.6%), much (23.3%), and somewhat (10.0%) emulate cartoon characters' "Body Moments."

Table 4.4 Statistics, Correlations

	Watch cartoon	Copy Cartoon Dress	Copy Cartoon Language	Copy Cartoon Eating Style	Copy Body Moments
Watch Cartoon	1	.015	.050	.081	.023
		.822	.445	.209	.723
N	240	240	240	240	

*No. of responses (n=240)

This data is about whether watching cartoons has any relationship with certain behaviors children might copy, such as dress, language, eating habits, or body movements. The key value to look at in this kind of analysis is the p-value. If the p-value is less than 0.05, it usually means the relationship is statistically significant in simple terms, the behavior is likely influenced by watching cartoons. The relationship

between watching cartoons and copying cartoon dress has a p-value of 0.822. This is much higher than 0.05, which means there is **no significant link** between watching cartoons and copying cartoon dress. The relationship between watching cartoons and copying cartoon language has a p-value of 0.445. Again, this is **not significant**, so children are not clearly influenced to copy the language from cartoons just because they

watch them. The relationship between watching cartoons and copying eating style shows a p-value of 0.209. This also does **not show a meaningful relationship**. It means watching cartoons doesn't have a strong influence on how children eat. Finally, the connection between watching cartoons and copying body movements has a p-value of 0.723. This is also

not significant, indicating no strong link between watching cartoons and children imitating movements. In summary, based on the data, there is **no statistically significant evidence** that watching cartoons leads children to copy dress, language, eating styles, or body movements.

Figure 4.5 Children Academic performance

The children's grades from the prior class are displayed in figure 4.4. According to an examination of children's academic performance overall, the majority of students receive a "Grade B" score of 27.1%, which is much higher than the grades of B+ (26.3%), A (19.6%), C (11.3%), A+ (7.9%), D (7.1%), and F (0.8%).

Table 4.5 Statistics, Correlations

	Watch Cartoon Movies	effects on eyesight weakness	Effects on Obesity	Effects on Sleep Disorder
Watch Cartoon Movies Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	1	.216	.138	.178
		.098	.294	.174
N	240	60	60	60

*No. of responses (n=240)

This data presents the relationship between watching cartoons or movies and three possible health effects in children: eyesight weakness, obesity, and sleep disorders. The method used to examine these relationships is called Pearson correlation, which helps determine how strongly two things are related. There is weak positive relationship between watching cartoons or

movies and the development of weak eyesight. This means that as the time spent watching cartoons or movies increases, eyesight weakness also tends to increase slightly. However, this relationship is not statistically significant, meaning the result could have happened by chance and we cannot confidently say there's a real effect. The connection between watching

cartoons or movies and obesity is very weak. The correlation is small, and again, the result is not statistically significant.

This means watching cartoons or movies does not show a meaningful or reliable relationship with obesity in this study. There is small positive relationship between cartoon/movie watching and sleep disorders. This suggests that more screen time might slightly increase the chances of having sleep issues. But once again, the relationship is not statistically significant, so we cannot be sure this is a real effect. Although watching cartoons and movies shows weak connections with eyesight issues, obesity, and sleep problems, none of these links are strong or statistically proven in this data. Therefore, we cannot confidently say that watching cartoons or movies causes any of these health problems based on this study alone. In Eyesight Weakness, the correlation value is 0.216, which shows a weak positive relationship.

This means that as cartoon/movie watching increases, eyesight weakness also slightly increases. The p-value is 0.098, which is greater than 0.05, so this relationship is not statistically significant. This means the result might have occurred by chance. Although, the correlation is 0.138, indicating a very weak positive relationship between watching cartoons/movies and obesity. The p-value is 0.294, which is much greater than 0.05, so this result is not significant, and we cannot rely on it and sleep disorder, the correlation is 0.178, suggesting a weak positive relationship between watching cartoons/movies and sleep problems. The p-value is 0.174, which is also greater than 0.05, so this relationship is not statistically significant either.

Summary

The results also demonstrate strong positive relationship between watching cartoons and imitating cartoon characters in terms of eating habits, attire, language, and body parts. The examination of the data pertaining to children's preferences for cartoon elements revealed that, on the whole, children prefer

to imitate the "dresses" and "language" of their favorite cartoon characters more than they do their eating habits and body parts. Subsequent data analysis revealed that girls are much more likely than boys to imitate the language of cartoon characters. children's preference for cartoon characters in relation to imitation dresses indicates that urban female children between the ages of 5 and 8 have strong affinity for cartoon and maintain steady focus on dresses. It was noted during the study that many children enjoy and imitate the eating habits of cartoon characters. The data analysis also revealed that very young children participated in coping body moments. Cartoon exposure has a significant effect on children's perceptions and outputs, making it a crucial research variable. In contrast to their acquisition of love and sharing behavior, problem-solving abilities, and political awareness, children acquire a second language (English and Hindi) via cartoons, according to overall empirical data.

The study's most significant variable was the academic performance of the children. The statistical results pertaining to the children's exposure to cartoons and their academic performance indicate a highly significant positive correlation between the two, as measured by the grades they received. This is consistent with data from 1920–30 pane fund studies that found numerous other factors, such as the parents' educational background, the children's interactions with their family, classmates, teachers, society, and all other social actors, interact with the academic performance of the children. According to the data, children who watch cartoons for less than an hour are more likely to receive A+, A, B+, B, C, D, and F grades; therefore, children who watch cartoons for less than an hour are more likely to receive B+ grades.

The research also examined children's perceptions of the actual world and their imaginations.

A minority of the children believed that cartoons depicted the real world, or that they had their own world somewhere in the deep sea or the skies. According to studies on parents' restrictions on their children' access to cartoon movies, the majority of children have some restrictions from their parents. An analysis of the data by age revealed that parents place more restrictions on children in lower age groups (5-8 years old) and lower education levels (primary school)

than on children in higher age and educational groups. A correlation test was used to assess the relationship between parental control over their children's cartoon movie viewing and the limitations placed on them. The statistical results indicated a significant relationship between parental control and children's cartoon viewing restrictions, suggesting that parental restriction could effectively control children's cartoon movie viewing. In order to find out what the parents thought about the effects of cartoon movies, a questionnaire was also created for them. The study's most significant variable is the children's attention span. The results indicated that children focus far more on cartoon movies than on academics, games, or any other activity. Parents of children from various living area groups hold differing opinions. According to statistical studies, children's eyesight deteriorates significantly when they watch cartoons. The exclusive analysis of the relationship between obesity and eye weakness.

Suggestions for Further Studies

- Using an experimental approach, a focus group may be organized to examine how cartoons affect children.
- A panel sample of cartoons may be used to do a content study on the effects of cartoons on children.
- A research based on factual information and field observations may be created to record the whole range of personality changes that children experience as a result of viewing cartoons.
- Additional research on the cartoon aspects that influence the behaviors and educational experiences of diverse kid groups should look at topics including school grades, health, and child personality determinants.
- Future studies might be carried out to determine the ongoing behavioral changes that children are experiencing as a result of television in general and cartoons in particular.
- To determine the extent of the effects of cartoon viewing on children's emotional development, a comparison study might be created.
- This study was limited by the fact that data was gathered from a specific subset of children who were less diverse. Given that children generally have diverse perceptions of these questions, this might be problematic. For instance, it's possible that children have a more positive outlook on cartoons and their effects.
- To address present and future patterns of behavioral changes in children, further study from a variety of angles is required.

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